

EFFICACY OF ABAMECTIN AND DIAFENTHIURON IN CONTROLLING THRIPS AND MITES IN MULBERRY

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Abstract

An experiment to evaluate abamectin 1.9% EC and diafenthiuron 50% WP for safety period on mulberry silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. was conducted and fed to the silkworms at different days after spraying (DAS) pesticides. Among tested chemicals, diafenthiuron 50% WP at 1 g/lit and abamectin 1.9 % EC at 0.75 ml/lit exhibited maximum control on thrips population till 21 DAS (1.03 thrips/leaf in diafenthiuron 50% WP and 0.98 thrips/leaf in abamectin 1.9% EC on 21 DAS) indicating their efficacy for managing the thrips in mulberry. The molecules with novel mode of action, diafenthiuron 50% WP and abamectin 1.9% EC also exhibited maximum control on population of mites till 21 DAS (0.29, 0.26, 0.79, 0.69 and 0.89 mites per 2 cm² in diafenthiuron 50% WP and 0.13, 0.18, 0.65, 0.52 and 0.83 mites per 2 cm² in abamectin 1.9% EC, respectively, at 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS) on par with an absolute acaricide, cynopyrafen 30% EC at 0.5 ml/lit (1.15, 2.03, 2.01, 1.82 and 1.59 mites per 2 cm² on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS, respectively) indicating their efficacy for managing both thrips and mites with a single spray in mulberry. Further, these chemicals did not produce any phytotoxicity symptoms on mulberry plant at 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS indicating their suitability for safe use in mulberry for effective management of thrips and mites.

Keywords: Novel insecticide, Mulberry thrips and mites, sucking pests

Introduction

Mulberry (*Morus* spp.) is a versatile, fast-growing deciduous tree that is believed to have originated in the Himalayan foothills of India and China (Khan *et al.*, 2013; Yuan and Zhao, 2017; Rohela *et al.*, 2020). Mulberry is a unique plant that can adapt to a wide range of climates, soil conditions, and altitudes ranging from 0 to 4000 meters above sea level (Sarkar *et al.*, 2017) and has over 1000 cultivated varieties, mainly in Asia (Sanchez, 2001). Southern Indian states like Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Kerala have embraced sericulture, dedicating approximately 2,42,244 hectares to mulberry cultivation. However, the industry faces significant threats from sucking pests in mulberry cultivation thrips are causing 42.55% of infestation are identified followed by mealy bugs 20.88%. Globally, 35 species of thrips pose a substantial threat and 21 of them in India. Mites, once considered as minor pests are now cause 5-10% of damage, worsened by climate change, creating a severe mite and thrips complex in sericulture regions. Climate change exacerbates this problem, impacting cocoon production and industry sustainability, demanding urgent measures to safeguard mulberry cultivation and the silk industry's future.

The management option to address several pests in mulberry was limited with regard to chemical control using chemical *viz.*, dichlorvos 76% EC and dimethoate 30% EC., which have been a versatile insecticide for controlling several pests including sucking insects (Mahadeva, 2011). However, the Indian government imposed a complete ban on dichlorvos 76% EC usage from December 31, 2020 (Anonymous, 2016). Another chemical option, dimethoate 30% EC, an organophosphorus compound, although also used, against

Treatment details:

Treatments	Group	Mode of Action	Dosage
T ₁	Diafenthiuron 50% WP	Thiourea derivatives	1 g/lit
T ₂	Abamectin 1.9% EC	Macrocyclic lactones	0.75 ml/lit
T ₃	Diamethoate 30% EC	Organophosphate group	2 ml/lit
T ₄	Cyanypyrafen 30% EC	Pyrazole group	Mitochondrial electron transport inhibitor (METI)
T ₅	Azadirachtin 10000 ppm	Limonoid group	Anti-feedant
T ₆	Control (water spray)	-	-
T ₇	Absolute control	-	-

A. Thrips

A total of three leaves were collected from different canopy level at 3rd, 5th and 7th position from apex in each replication of different treatments. The number of thrips was counted in each leaf and represented as number of thrips per leaf (Mallinath, 2019) (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

thrips and lacked acaricidal properties for management of mites. Further, the pesticide use pattern in the present-day situation has led to pesticide residues in the harvestable produce and harm to non-target organisms. To address these issues, newer and safer pesticides with different modes of action are needed. Abamectin (Avermectin B1) and diafenthiuron (1-tert-butyl-3-(2,6-diisopropyl) thio-urea) are two such molecules with novel insecticidal and acaricidal properties, acting as neurotoxins (abamectin) or by impacting metabolic processes like respiration (diafenthiuron). Abamectin 1.9% EC is effective against various mites and insect pests in agriculture and horticulture (Lasota and Dybas, 1990). Diafenthiuron 50% WP has shown effectiveness against whiteflies, aphids, thrips, and more in crops like brinjal, tomato, chillies, cotton and cardamom (Stanley *et al.*, 2016). It's also proven effective against thrips and mites in mulberry (Kalpana *et al.*, 2022). Present study aims to evaluate these two molecules exhibiting dual pesticidal properties while considering their compatibility with silkworms and native natural predators in the mulberry ecosystem.

Materials and methods**Experimental layout**

The experiment was laid out in a well-established V-1 mulberry garden following Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with 7 treatments and four replications. The population of mites and thrips were recorded one day before and 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 days after spraying (DAS) of the chemicals by visual scoring method. A total of five plants were selected and tagged in each replication for recording the observations regarding infestation of thrips and mites.

B. Mites

A total of three leaves were collected from the 3rd, 5th and 7th position from apex at random from each replication of different treatments and were taken to the laboratory in zip lock polythene covers and observations under stereo zoom microscope (BSM350). The number of eggs and active stages of mites present in a 2 cm² window were

counted and recorded as number of mites per 2 cm² (Sharath *et al.*, 2022) (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Statistical analysis

The data collected from the experimental field and silkworm rearing were analyzed statistically by using one-way RCBD and CRD for testing of significance by Fisher's method of analysis of variance as outlined by Sundaraj *et al.* (1972). The level of significance used in the F-test was P = 0.05. The critical difference (CD) values were computed to compare significance of the treatments.

Results and Discussion

Abamectin 1.9% EC and diafenthiuron 50% WP are the new generation chemicals with a label claim against sucking pests (mites, aphid, thrips and mealy bug) in several agri-horticultural plants. The efficacy of these two chemicals with novel mode of action was assessed in mulberry maintained at the Department of Sericulture, GKVK for effective management of thrips and mites and the observation are documented in this section.

Population of thrips (No./leaf) in mulberry at different days after spray of selected chemicals

The pesticides, abamectin 1.9% EC and diafenthiuron 50% WP were sprayed on mulberry during three seasons (Jan-Feb, Mar-April and May-June 2023). The pre-spray observations were recorded on one day before spray of the chemical (21.28 thrips/leaf) and the post spray count was recorded on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 days after spray (DAS) separately for each treatment. The population of thrips (No./leaf) recorded significantly minimum upon spraying of diafenthiuron 50% WP at 1 g/lit (0.52, 0.69, 0.97, 0.60, 1.03 thrips/leaf) and abamectin 1.9% EC at 0.75 ml/lit (0.29, 0.43, 0.63, 0.58, 0.98 thrips/leaf), respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS on par with dimethoate 30% EC at different durations of spray (1.14, 1.22, 1.97, 0.98, 1.34 thrips/leaf, respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS and 21.65, 21.94, 22.38, 24.12 and 23.26 thrips/leaf, respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS where no chemical was sprayed (Table 1).

Considering the average of three seasons, the chemical, dimethoate 30% EC though exhibited maximum control on the population of thrips till 8 DAS, their effectiveness was reduced thereafter that is reflected through increasing in the number of thrips recorded on 15 DAS onwards. However, the tested chemicals, diafenthiuron 50% WP and abamectin 1.9% EC exhibited maximum control on population of thrips indicating their efficacy for managing thrips in mulberry (Fig. 3).

Population of mites (No./2 cm²) in mulberry at different days after spray of selected chemicals

The pre-spray count on population of mites was recorded on a day before spraying of the chemical that was 6.98 mites per 2 cm² window. The post spray count of the population of mites was recorded on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS separately for each treatment.

The population of mites (No./2 cm²) recorded significantly minimum upon spraying abamectin 1.9% EC (@ 0.75 ml/l) (0.13, 0.18, 0.65, 0.52 and 0.83 mites/2cm²), diafenthiuron 50% WP at 1 g/lit (0.29, 0.26, 0.79, 0.69 and 0.89 mites/2 cm²) respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS on par with cyenopyrafen 30% EC at 0.5 ml/lit (1.15, 2.03, 2.01, 1.82 and 1.59 mites/2 cm²), respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS. The maximum number of mites was reported on absolute control (10.54, 10.58, 10.55, 10.96 and 11.20 mites/2 cm², respectively on 1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS where no chemical or water was sprayed (Table 2).

Irrespective of seasons, among the new generation chemicals tested against mites in mulberry, diafenthiuron 50% WP and abamectin 1.9% EC recorded maximum control of mites, that were statistically on par with the recommended acaricide cyenopyrafen 30% EC at all the durations of spray (1, 3, 8, 15 and 21 DAS, respectively) (Fig. 4). Diamethoate 30% EC which is an acetylcholinesterase inhibitor affecting the central and peripheral nervous system and found effective against a wide range of sucking pests, including aphids, whiteflies, mealybugs and thrips. It disrupts their nervous system, leading to paralysis and mortality (Sujatha and Bharpoda, 2017).

It is also known to possess acaricidal property according to label claim of the chemical (https://agrosshopy.com/index.php?route=product/product&product_id=88). Cyenopyrafen 30% SC is an acaricide and a Mitochondrial Electron Transport Inhibitor (METI) that operates through a novel mode of action by targeting complex II in the mitochondrial electron transport chain (<https://irac-online.org/active-ingredient/cyenopyrafen/>) responsible for utilizing the energy released during oxidation to facilitate ATP synthesis required for essential cellular processes. Consequently, the inhibition of this process leads to the death of mites (Hayashi *et al.*, 2013). The chemicals abamectin 1.9% EC and diafenthiuron 50% WP with novel mode of action have shown promising results with their dual insecticidal and acaricidal properties. Diafenthiuron 50% WP has a novel mode of action involving inhibition mitochondrial respiration (Muhammad *et al.*, 2013), while abamectin 1.9% EC stimulates the release of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA) leading to paralysis in the muscles. Hence, their ingestion results in rapid paralysis and subsequent death of mite and insect pests (Reddy *et al.*, 2014).

Conclusion

Mites and thrips mostly occur simultaneously on mulberry during dry seasons. Hence focussing on management of these pests with the application of single chemical molecule would be more beneficial. Among the selected chemicals, abamectin 1.9% EC at 0.75 ml/lit and diafenthiuron 50% WP at 1 g/lit were found best for management of both mites and thrips in a single application Hence, abamectin 1.9% EC at 0.75 ml/lit and diafenthiuron 50% WP at 1 g/lit can be used as an alternate molecule to DDVP 76% EC for managing both mulberry thrips and mites.

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Table 1: Population of Thrips per leaf at different days after spray of selected chemical molecules in mulberry

Treatments		Number of thrips per leaf				
		1DAS	3 DAS	8DAS	15 DAS	21 DAS
T ₁	Diafenthiuron 50% WP	0.52 ^c	0.69 ^c	0.97 ^{bc}	0.60 ^c	1.03 ^{cd}
T ₂	Abamectin 1.9% EC	0.29 ^c	0.43 ^c	0.63 ^{bc}	0.58 ^c	0.98 ^{cd}
T ₃	Diamethoate 30% EC	1.14 ^c	1.22 ^c	1.97 ^c	0.98 ^c	1.34 ^d
T ₄	Cyenopyrafen 30% EC	3.29 ^b	4.21 ^b	7.40 ^b	4.26 ^{bc}	6.60 ^b
T ₅	Azadirachtin 10000 ppm	2.13 ^c	2.95 ^{bc}	3.03 ^{bc}	5.86 ^b	4.73 ^{bc}
T ₆	Control (water spray)	18.00 ^a	20.15 ^a	21.55 ^a	22.74 ^a	22.30 ^a
T ₇	Absolute control	21.65 ^a	21.94 ^a	22.38 ^a	24.12 ^a	23.26 ^a
F-test		*	*	*	*	*
S. Em ±		1.82	1.91	1.45	1.31	1.43
CD 0.05		3.81	4.39	4.94	4.21	5.10
CV		8.45	9.74	9.76	15.11	15.26

Prespray count: 21.28 thrips/leaf; DAS: Days after spraying;

*Significant at 0.05; Numbers superscripted with same alphabets are statistically on par.

Table 2: Population of mites/2cm² at different days after spray of selected chemical molecules in mulberry.

Treatments		Number of mites/2cm ²				
		1 DAS	3 DAS	8 DAS	15 DAS	21 DAS
T ₁	Diafenthiuron 50% WP	0.29 ^b	0.26 ^b	0.79 ^c	0.69 ^{bc}	0.89 ^c
T ₂	Abamectin 1.9% EC	0.13 ^b	0.18 ^b	0.65 ^c	0.52 ^{bc}	0.83 ^c
T ₃	Diamethoate 30% EC	1.51 ^b	2.36 ^b	3.07 ^b	1.80 ^b	1.84 ^b
T ₄	Cyenopyrafen 30% EC	1.15 ^b	2.03 ^b	2.01 ^c	1.82 ^c	1.59 ^c
T ₅	Azadirachtin 10000 ppm	1.45 ^b	2.98 ^b	1.88 ^{bc}	2.54 ^b	3.48 ^b
T ₆	Control (water spray)	6.58 ^a	7.25 ^a	9.41 ^a	8.18 ^a	8.87 ^a
T ₇	Absolute control	7.72 ^a	8.30 ^a	10.50 ^a	10.23 ^a	11.36 ^a
F-test		*	*	*	*	*
S. Em ±		1.05	1.58	1.26	0.92	1.29
CD 0.05		3.15	4.32	3.77	3.30	4.54
CV		7.54	10.56	11.33	14.79	23.62

Pre-spray count: 6.97 mites/2cm²; DAS: Days after spraying

*Significant at 0.05; Numbers superscripted with same alphabets are statistically on par.

LIST OF FIGURES:

A. *Polyphagotarsonemus latus*

B. *Tetranychus urticae*

C. *Pseudodendrothrips mori*

D. Mites and thrips

Fig. 1: Mites and thrips species in mulberry

Fig. 2: Symptoms of thrips and mites infested mulberry leaves

Fig. 3: Population of thrips (No./ leaf) in mulberry at different days of spray of the selected chemicals

Fig. 4: Population of mites (No./ per 2 cm²) in mulberry at different days of spray of the selected chemical.